

AN ENGINEERING VISION ABOUT ACOUSTIC FATIGUE IN COMPOSITE MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

According to the literature, of the early 60's until the mid 80's, there were few data on theoretical development about acoustic fatigue. By this time, abacus based on simple theoretical models has been developed for usual aircraft structures of the time. The use of advanced composites in the 80's motivated the development of more sophisticated theoretical models due to the versatility of projects with these materials. As noted in the literature, tests and theoretical investigations were carried out. The new investigation was to minimize the differences found in abacus with the existing theoretical results and numerical simulations by finite elements. The challenges were predicting nonlinear behaviour. Due to the complexity of the tests and the number of parameters involved in the analysis a simple and user friendly tool for analysis is desirable to have. With this tool is possible to analyze easier the laminates definition of an aircraft component subjected to acoustic loading as a preliminary design. Within this context, the objective of this article is to present a sensibility study about composite acoustic fatigue behaviour through a simple tool. The theory is based on classical theory for composite materials. The proposed methodology is to evaluate the durability of composite panels subjected to acoustic loading. The major contributions of this study are the inclusion of aircraft flight operating conditions and engine data in the analysis results. Also, theoretical results of Sound Pressure Level (SPL) compared with experimental results are shown too. The results showed good correlation for a given frequency level. In a simple way, the analysis procedure developed lets to increase efficiency and productivity in engineering processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the late 1950s, cracks in the skin were reported in jet aircraft structures near the engines according Clarkson (1994), ref. [1]. These incidents alerted the industry and research centers with the possibility of problems that could arise with future aircraft equipped with more powerful engines. Even with comprehensive maintenance programs to ensure the life of the aircraft, the feeling that a catastrophic failure was going to happen, bothered everyone. Thus, theoretical studies and tests on plane and curved plates were initiated. With the possibility of reproducing the effects of maximum intensity of the noise, aircraft manufacturers and research centers initiated testing in representative parts of the aircraft structure. Pressure and deformation measurements were made in these tests using a jet engine to allow a realistic acoustic excitation. The onset and propagation cracks were recorded. Simple theoretical models and processes of excitation were made taking into account the available resources of time. Powell (1958), ref. [2] developed a formulation for linear normal mode and Miles (1954), ref. [3] showed results considering fatigue mode aspects. As a result of the initial research, simple models were then developed to guide designs considering the effects of acoustic loading. The probability of failure due to high operating temperatures for some aircraft configurations combined with acoustic conditions generated a new problem with the widespread use of composite materials: Due the possibility of working with large displacements, the acoustic behaviour became non-linear problem and coupled with high temperatures the thermal buckling could occur. New theoretical studies were then initiated. Even so, the simulations were very conservative with response rates around the factor of 2. Therefore investigations suggested minimize the differences of abacus with the existing

theoretical results and numerical simulations by finite elements.

In Cunningham (2004), ref. [4], a design review for acoustic fatigue in relation to aircraft structures is presented. The methods are based on linear theories and a single degree of freedom. This method with the finite element method to predict the deformation of double curvature sandwich panel under acoustic excitation is also discussed. Recent developments of methods considering nonlinear dynamic response of structures with acoustic thermal effects are also mentioned. For future directions in the acoustic fatigue research area suggestions were made. It is evident the interest in dynamic response of aircraft structures subjected to high intensity acoustic loads. It should be noted an effort to predict nonlinear response of structures under the high intensity loads pressure levels. However the authors suggest other interesting investigations. For example, structures experimental data, acoustically excited with high levels up to 175 dB for combined static and thermo acoustic loads. Although it has been advances in simulation, the representation of acoustic loads and their accuracy is a field to be explored. More investigations should be developed to facilitate computational aero-acoustic interfaces with finite element analysis or other method of prediction. In accordance with the proposed method, the author concludes that there is a good correlation between the test and the theoretical prediction for rms deformation value. The method is similar to adopted by ESDU (2011), ref. [5], Thompson (1972), ref. [6] and Blevins (1989), ref. [7]. It is clear that there is interest in the project under acoustic fatigue due to increased sound pressure level (SPL), the use of composite materials and in hyper-sonic vehicles projects interest.

The analysis and substantiation criteria increase with the use of composite materials because the parameters are more encompassing. For example, in Adams (1973), ref. [8], theoretical studies were carried out to determine the effect of fiber orientation and geometry in laminate damping behaviour considering the bending, twisting and modulus of elasticity effect. Materials off-axis ($+\Theta$), angle-ply ($\pm\Theta$) and cross-ply ($0/90^\circ$) were investigated. The effects of shear stress, longitudinal and transverse stress in damping behaviour were examined by energy dissipation. It was evident that the shear stress is the predominant factor that generates high damping. The transverse stress sometimes generates high energy dissipation while the longitudinal stress results in a minimum or even negligible. An important fact to note is that in most of the cases studied there was a good correlation between the theoretical prediction and experimental results.

Therefore, the objective of this paper is to present the composite acoustic fatigue sensibility analysis considering durability. The procedure was developed based on the assumptions of engineering reports, reference [9] and the ESDU, refs. [10], [11], [12], [13] and [14]. The analysis tool developed in partnership with Sarae (2007), ref. [15], combines various procedures in a simple manner, thereby increasing efficiency and productivity in the engineering processes.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology is based on the purpose of evaluating the durability of composite panels subjected to acoustic loading. The analysis process is shown in Figure 1. It is important to emphasize the references ESDU (Engineering Sciences Data Unit), 84027 (1984) and 93027 (1993) and the airplane operating conditions, including flight and engine data.

The development is based on the following assumptions:

1. The predominant form of the panel vibration in the fundamental mode is fixed edge,
2. The pressure is uniform and is in phase and the level of sound pressure spectrum is constant in the frequency range near the natural frequency,
3. The deformation varies linearly along the thickness,
4. The laminates are symmetrical and balanced,
5. The dimensions of the panels (length, width and thickness, i.e., "a", "b" and "t" respectively) satisfy the following conditions:

$$b/t \leq 200. \quad (1)$$

$$1.5 \leq a/b \leq 3.0 \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 –Flow Chart Process.

The assumptions regarding the fundamental natural frequency were: (a) panel subjected to loads in the plane according to Figure 2 and (b) can be simply supported or clamped. The Rayleigh Ritz method was used for natural frequency determination. In case of compression loading the compressive load does not exceed 30% of the initial buckling load as mentioned in Lambert (1990), ref. [16].

Figure 2 – Panel in Plane Loads.

It is noted that is preferable to have the value of specific damping determined experimentally as mentioned in ESDU 73011 (1973). The value of the damping (δ) can be estimated according to the following definition.

$$\delta = \frac{\Delta U}{U} = \frac{\text{energy_dissipated}}{\text{maximum_strain_energy}} \quad (3)$$

In case of small vibration amplitudes the damping is independent of the amplitude of the stress cycle. It is further assumed that the effects in the plane loads due to bending are neglected, as mentioned in ESDU 85012 (1985).

Following the flow chart of Figure 1, the estimate of the response of the structure with respect to rms (Root Mean Square) strain, is given by equation (4).

$$S_{rms} = \left[\frac{\pi}{4\delta} f_n G_p(f_n) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} S_0 \quad (4)$$

$$\epsilon_{rms} = \epsilon_{fn}(S_{rms}) \times K_p \times K_c$$

Where, δ is the equivalent damping ratio, f_n is the natural frequency, $G_p(f_n)$ is the spectral density of the acoustic pressure, S_0 is the stress ratio of the static pressure applied, ϵ_{fn} is the rms strain

deducted from S_{rms} , K_p and K_c are correction factors derived empirically. The Figure 3 shows the points where the rms strains are estimated. In the J.Born (2006), ref. [17], the rms strain value obtained by ESDU agrees very well with the finite element analysis.

Figure 3 – Estimated rms Strain Location.

The number of cycles to failure (N_r) due to fatigue under rms strain estimated by equation (4), can be obtained in accordance with the ESDU 84027 (1984) and 93027 (1993). The data are presented in strain rather than stress to minimize the effect of laminate orientation. Also due to the dispersion of the results the factor 3 sigma (standard deviation) was used in this development for safety margin. In accordance with ESDU 84027 (1984) the failure location is in the run out stiffener bonded in the skin.

Assuming the Palmgren-Miner rule the accumulated damage are calculated according to equation (5).

$$D = SF \cdot \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{N_{req}^i}{N_r^i} \right) < 1 \quad (5)$$

where D is the cumulative damage, SF is the scatter factor, N_r is the number of cycles to failure related to strain acting on the rms "i" phase of the flight, N_{req} is the number of cycles occurring in the "i" phase during the flight life of the aircraft and "n" is the number of flight phases.

3 VALIDATION

In order to validate the estimated SPL by ESDU 99006, ref. [18], the experimental results showed in the reference [9] was used. In this reference, one point where the SPL was measured and used by this validation is shown in the Figure 4. In accordance with the Figure 5, the theoretical SPL agree very well with experimental results until the frequency 2000 Hz. Another conclusion based in the theoretical results is the minor contribution of the temperature ($T_{js}=600K$ to $800K$).

Figure 4 – SPL Measure Point.

Figure 5 – SPL Experimental x Theoretical Results.

4 APPLICATION

Based in the estimated SPL discussed in the previous paragraph, one point showed in the Figure 6, was chosen to equation (5) application.

Figure 6 – Panel Location: #1 Fwd Fuselage.

The N_{req} i.e., the number of cycles occurring in the "i" phase during the flight life of the aircraft and "n" the number of flight phases were extracted from the reference [9]. As observed in the Figure 7, in the interest point the cumulative damage is insignificant. In addition the climb, cruise and descent phases are the most significant contributions in this cumulative damage.

$$Cumulative_Damage = \sum_i D_i = 2.8E-09$$

Figure 7 – Cumulative Damage #1 – Flight Phase Contribution.

5 SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The advantage to have a simplified analysis is the possibility to make a quick sensitivity analysis. In this paper two cases are analyzed for laminates with the same thickness: (a) the sensitivity of stacking sequence and (b) sensitivity of the loads in the plane, considering number of cycles to failure. The material is carbon/epoxy. The panel dimensions are 400x200 mm, length (a) by width (b). The Figures 8 and 9, show the results. Considering the cross-ply laminate as the reference, as noted in the Figure 8, the stacking sequence is better for quasi-isotropic material in the number of cycles to failure. Then considering the laminate quasi-isotropic and no running loads in the plane as the reference, as observed in the Figure 9, the compression and shear loads increase more the number of cycles to failure than tension load. The analysis showed is for the point #2, of the Figure 3.

Figure 8: Stacking Sequence Sensitivity Analysis.

Figure 9: Running Loads Sensitivity Analysis.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The simplified procedure based in the classical theory permits explore the range of options. The sensibility analysis showed that the number of cycles to failure is affected by the stacking sequence and the running loads characteristics. Based in the results presented it is observed that for commercial regional jet, the composite acoustic fatigue does not seem to be critical. It should be pointed out that the non linear behaviour and the temperature influence were not analyzed.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B.L. Clarkson, Review of Sonic Fatigue Technology, *NASA Contractor Report 4587*, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, U.S.A., April 1994.
- [2] A. Powell, On the Fatigue Failure of Structures due to Vibrations Excited by Random Pressure Fields, *JASA* 30, pp 1130-1135, 1958.
- [3] J.W. Miles, On Structural Fatigue under Random Loading, *J. Aero Sc.* 21, No. 11, pp 753-762, 1954.
- [4] P.R. Cunningham and R.G. White, A Review of Analytical Methods for Aircraft Structures Subjected to High-Intensity Random Acoustic Loads, *J. Aerospace Engineering*, Vol. 218, Part G, pp 231-242, 2004.
- [5] ESDU Committee, Engineering Sciences Data Unit, *ESDUscope*, v4.9.2.0, Release Level 2011-07, London, UK, 2011.
- [6] A. G. R. Thompson and R. F. Lambert, The Estimation of RMS Stresses in Stiffened Skin Panels Subjected to Random Acoustic Loading, *Technical Report Section 5, AGARD-AG-162*, Advisory Group for Aerospace Research and Development, NATO, November 1972.
- [7] R. D. Blevins, An approximate method for sonic fatigue analysis of plates and shells. *J. Sound Vibration*, 1989, 129(1), 51–71.
- [8] R.D. Adams and D.G.C. Bacon, Effect of Fiber Orientation and Laminate Geometry on the Dynamic Properties of CFRP, *J. Composite Materials*, Vol. 7 (October 1973), p.402, 1973.
- [9] F.K. Arakaki, G.G. Momm and L.B. Oliveira, Composite Acoustic Fatigue Criteria, *EMBRAER Technical Report 170SRY114*, Sept 2004.
- [10] ESDU Committee, Damping in Acoustically Excited Structures, *ESDU 73011*, London, UK, July 1973.
- [11] ESDU Committee, Endurance of Fiber-Reinforced Composite, Laminated Structural Elements Subjected to Simulated Random Acoustic Loading, London, *ESDU 84027*, UK, 1984.
- [12] ESDU Committee, Estimation of Damping in Laminated and Fibre-Reinforced Plates, *ESDU 85012*, London, UK, June 1985.
- [13] ESDU Committee, Method of Testing for Endurance of Structural Elements Using Simulated Acoustic Loading, London, *ESDU 93027*, UK, 1993.
- [14] ESDU Committee, Computer-based Estimation Procedure for Near-field Single-stream Jet Noise, *ESDU 99006*, London, UK, Nov 2007.
- [15] W. Sarae and S.W. Tsai, Estimation of Acoustic Fatigue Endurance, Tool#3 Development, *Composites Design Group, Department of Aeronautics & Astronautics*, Stanford University, 2007.
- [16] R.F. Lambert, et al, A Rayleigh-Ritz method of analysis for vibrations of orthotropic plates under static in-plane loading (including shear), *Memorandum No.71, ESDU International plc*, London, UK, August 1990.
- [17] J. Born da Silva, Estimation of the Effective Strain in Laminates Panels Subjected to Random Acoustics Load, *Professional Master's Thesis, Technological Institute of Aeronautics - ITA*, Sao Jose dos Campos, Brazil, 2006.
- [18] ESDU Committee, Computer-based estimation procedure for near-field single-stream jet noise, *ESDU 99006*, London, UK, 2011.